

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF NOVEL HIGH TG POLYIMIDE MATRIX CARBON FIBRE-REINFORCED LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, an assessment of the mechanical performance of a newly developed carbon fibre-reinforced polyimide composite system T650/NEXIMID[®] MHT-R is presented. This system was subjected to a series of mechanical tests at ambient temperature in order to determine the tensile, compressive, flexural and interlaminar shear properties. Moreover, an additional testing campaign was conducted, using a T650/NEXIMID[®] MHT-R laminate in which the sizing had been thermally removed prior to manufacturing, in order to investigate the effect of fiber treatment on the mechanical performance. The experimental results indicated that the T650/NEXIMID[®] MHT-R composites along with exceptionally high T_g (~370-420°C) exhibited very good elastic properties in comparison with other polyimide and epoxy-based systems and, although slightly lower than the best results from literature, promising strength values. Finally, the thermal removal of the sizing did not affect the tensile, compression and flexural properties, however the interlaminar shear strength was significantly deteriorated.

1 INTRODUCTION

The majority of high performance fibre-reinforced composites widely used in the aeronautics industry nowadays, utilise organic polymers like epoxies as matrix materials. These organic polymers at elevated temperatures begin to soften leading to a significant deterioration (up to 90% for matrix and fibre/matrix-dominated properties) of the mechanical performance while at even higher temperatures the overall integrity of the composite structure can be compromised since they start to decompose [1,2]. Therefore the temperature limitation these matrices pose, hinder the exploitation of the superior specific stiffness and strength composites materials exhibit over metallic alloys and ceramics. Polymers with glass transition temperatures above 300°C (cyanate esters and bismaleimides) or even over 400°C (phthalonitriles and polyimides), have been available for several years [3,4]. Moreover, attempts to utilise these types as matrices in fibre-reinforced composites have been reported, however, problems pertain to processability and brittleness have been noted whilst the mechanical characterisation has been deficient [3,4].

The strive for structures with high specific properties and high thermal stability has revived the research on polymers which could allow the development of fibre-reinforced composites capable of robust performance in the excess of 250°C. In line with this, the HicTac project (High performance composites for demanding high Temperature applications) funded by CleanSky has aimed in developing carbon fibre-reinforced/polyimide composites [5]. As part of the HicTac project, the current study reports the mechanical performance assessment of the T650/NEXIMID[®] MHT-R composite system. This polyimide-based composite system features the NEXIMID[®] MHT-R

thermosetting resin which has been recently developed within the HicTac project and exhibits a T_g above 400°C [6]. To assess the mechanical performance, tensile, compression, flexural and ILSS tests were conducted on a $[(-45/45)/(90/0)]_{2S}$ laminate and the properties were then compared against other commercial grade polyimide-based composites reported in the literature indicating comparable performance both in terms of stiffness and strength. An additional series of mechanical tests was carried out on a nominally identical laminate in which the sizing was thermally removed from the Thornel® T650 8-harness satin weave fabric with the aim to investigate the effect of sizing especially on the intralaminar properties, in light of studies on other commercial polyimides where the sizing had been removed prior to manufacturing [3,4,7,8]. Finally, fractographic analysis of ILSS specimens was employed to provide information about the dominant failure mechanisms and how the sizing influenced the failure process.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In the current chapter, a description of the material system used, specimen preparation as well as mechanical testing is provided.

2.1 Material Systems and Manufacturing

The material systems used in this study to investigate the effect of fibre sizing on the mechanical performance was the T650/NEXIMID® MHT-R. As reinforcement the Thornel® T650/35 8-harness satin woven fabric (370 g/m³) was used, supplied by Sigmatec while the fibres were produced by CYTEC [9] featuring a 1% UC.309 epoxy compatible sizing. With regards to the resin, the thermosetting polyimide NEXIMID® MHT-R was used which has exclusively been formulated for HicTac project by Nexam Chemical AB, Sweden (noted MHT-R hereafter). This polyimide is prepared using a combination of 6F-dianhydride (6-FDA) backbone, 4-(Phenylethynyl)Phthalic Anhydride (4-PEPA) end-group crosslinker and ethynyl bis-phthalic anhydride (EBPA) main chain crosslinker. One multidirectional laminate with dimensions 350×350 mm featuring a $[(-45/45)/(90/0)]_{2S}$ (eight fabric layers in total) layup was manufactured with Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) in stainless steel tool using a flow and pressure controlled injection piston supplied by ISOJET. This laminate was cured using the following curing protocol: melting and homogenization of the resin in the piston at 240°C for 30 minutes; degassing using vacuum at 240°C for 10 minutes; resin injection at 290°C; temperature increase to 340°C at a heating rate of 1.7°C/min, curing at 340°C for 0.5 h; temperature increase to 370°C at a heating rate of 1.7°C/min, curing at 370°C for 2 h, cooling down to 80°C during 12 h and demoulding. During curing, 12 Bar pressure was applied [6].

2.2 Sizing burn-off

Prior to layup and curing, the Thornel® T650 8-harness satin weave dry fabric layers were placed in an oven with controlled temperature to remove the UC.309 sizing. The burn-off of the sizing was carried out at 400°C for 30 min in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendation. Composite laminates containing de-sized (DS) fibres will henceforth be denoted DS-T650/MHT-R to distinguish from laminates made with as-received fibres (T650/MHT-R).

2.3 Quality Control

As soon as the T650/MHT-R laminate was manufactured, ultrasonic inspection was carried out using the RapidScan2 system, supplied by Sonatest. In addition, specimens from various locations throughout the laminate were extracted and used to assess the quality using optical microscopy. These specimens were ground and polished up to 1 µm grit size using a Struers Rotopol 1® polishing machine. Images of microstructure were obtained using a Nikon Eclipse LV150N optical microscope equipped with a Nikon DS-Fi2 camera, and processed using the Nikon NIS-Elements BR® software (v4.10).

2.4 Specimen Preparation

For the mechanical testing, specimens in various dimensions were cut using water-jet cutting: tension – 250×25 mm [10], flexure (three-point bending) – 125×10 mm [11], short-beam shear – 18×6 mm [12] and compression – 100×12 mm [13]. For the tensile and compression tests, woven glass fibre/epoxy tabs were glued on the specimens according to the respective standards [10,13].

2.5 Mechanical Testing

To assess the mechanical performance of these polyimide-based carbon fibre-reinforced composites and the effect of fibre sizing, tensile, compression, flexural and ILSS tests were conducted on both T650/MHT-R and DS-T650/MHT-R systems. Tensile testing was carried out on specimens with dimensions 250×25 mm according to ASTM D3039 [10] at a constant cross-head speed of 1 mm/min using an Instron 5801 servo-hydraulic machine equipped with a 100 kN load cell. The loading scheme comprised loading of the specimens up to 0.25% strain (extensometer reading), then unloading and subsequently reloading until failure. The stiffness calculation was carried out by linear fit of stress vs. strain curves on an interval between approximately 40MPa and 120MPa.

The compression testing of the T650/MHT-R specimens (80×12 mm) was performed using the classic Wyoming modified ITRII fixture [11]. Five specimens were loaded at 1 mm/min rate using an Instron 5801 servo-hydraulic machine equipped with a 100 kN load cell up to catastrophic failure and the strains were recorded on both sides by 5 mm strain gauges supplied by Kyowa (Resistance:120.0±0.8 Ohm – Gauge factor:2.09±1.0%). Calculation of stiffness was carried out by linear fit of stress vs. strain curves on a similar interval as the one used in tension (manually calculated average strain from both sides).

Subsequently, six specimens (125×10 mm) were tested under flexure in a three-point bending fixture according to ASTM D 7264 [12], at a constant cross-head speed of 1 mm/min using an Instron 5801 servo-hydraulic machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell. A 16:1 span-to-thickness ratio was used and the test was terminated as soon as the maximum strain in the outer surface of the test specimen reached 0.05 mm/mm or if break occurred prior to reaching the maximum strain. Similar to tensile and compression tests, calculation of stiffness was carried out by linear fit of stress vs. strain curves on an interval between approximately 40MPa and 120MPa.

Finally, for the short-beam shear test, eight specimens with dimensions 18×6 mm were tested in three-point bending with a 4:1 span-to-depth ratio [13] using an Instron 5801 servo-hydraulic machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell. The specimens were loaded at a rate of 1 mm/min until a 30% load drop or a two-piece specimen failure occurred or the head travel exceeded the specimen nominal thickness (approximately 3 mm).

3 RESULTS

In this section the results from the quality control and mechanical testing of the T650/MHT-R and DS-T650/MHT-R laminate are presented.

3.1 Quality Control

In Figure 2, the manufactured laminate can be seen side-by-side with the layout of the ultrasound amplitude throughout the laminate. The amplitude of the ultrasonic waves indicate a good quality especially towards the center and away from the free edges, where the input and output valves were positioned during manufacturing. In particular, in Figure 2 red color indicates absence of defects, whereas blue shades suggest presence of voids and possible delaminations. In addition, the optical microscopy also suggested that the laminate exhibited good quality as shown in Figure 2 which illustrates a representative micrograph from the cross section.

Figure 1: T650/MHT-R laminate (left); Amplitude of ultrasounds (%) throughout the laminate (right).

Figure 2: Representative cross section from the T650/MHT-R laminate acquired by optical microscopy.

3.2 Mechanical Testing

The mechanical properties of the two laminates are shown in Table 1 while representative stress-strain curves of the two laminates in tension, compression and 3-Point bending in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively, whilst load-displacement curves from the ILSS tests are presented in Figure 6.

In tension, the average stiffness was approximately 49 GPa (obtained in the unloading region) and the average strength was approximately 471 MPa. To ascribe a practical meaning to these results, strength values of 565 MPa of similar carbon fibre/polyimide composites (T800/PRM-15) have been reported in the literature [14]. In compression, the average stiffness and strength of the T650/MHT-R laminate in compression was approximately 45 GPa and 372 MPa respectively. In the literature, compressive strength values for multidirectional carbon fibre/polyimide composites have also been reported [3,14-16]; 378 MPa for T800/PRM-15, 442 MPa for unsized AS4/PETI-330 and 520 MPa for unsized T650/PETI-330. For the latter, a modulus of 42 GPa and 47 GPa respectively is reported.

In flexure, the average flexural stiffness and strength for the T650/MHT-R specimens were approximately 30 GPa and 485 MPa respectively, while the scatter was low indicating a highly controlled experimental procedure as well as a consistency in the specimen quality. In the literature, flexural stiffness and strength for multidirectional carbon fibre/polyimide unsized T650/PETI-330 multidirectional composites have been reported, 55 GPa and 694 MPa respectively (featuring a (+45/0/90/-45)_s layup though) [15]. The average interlaminar shear strength is approximately 48 MPa respectively. The ILSS of the T650/MHT-R system lie within the range of values reported in the literature for standard carbon/epoxy laminates [3,12-14].

Property/System	T650/MHT-R	DS-T650/MHT-R
Tension		
Stiffness (GPa)	48.5±0.6	45.2±0.9
Strength (MPa)	471.0±36.8	471.5±2.3
Strain-to-failure (%)	1.1±0.1	1.2±0.1
Compression		
Stiffness (GPa)	44.8±2.7	43.4±1.5
Strength (MPa)	371.3±14.8	367.1±13.1
Strain-to-failure (%)	0.9±0.1	0.9±0.1
3-Point bending		
Stiffness (GPa)	29.6±0.1	28.2±0.8
Strength (MPa)	485.0±24.8	482.5±23.1
Strain-to-failure (%)	1.9±0.2	2.2±0.2
Short-Beam Shear		
ILSS (MPa)	47.7±6.7	35.7±0.7

Table 1 Comparison of properties of laminates as-received and desized fibres.

Figure 3: Comparison of representative stress-strain curves in tension.

With regards to the mechanical performance of the DS-T650/MHT-R system (sizing thermally removed), considering the results shown in Table 1, the change of the mechanical properties in tension, compression and 3-Point bending was within experimental scatter, while only in short-beam shear a clear deterioration in the ILSS was observed upon removal of the fibre sizing. In tension, a 7% decrease was observed in the stiffness whilst no change was noted in strength (even though T650/MHT-R exhibited significantly higher scatter). In compression, the difference in the stiffness and strength between the two systems was low and within statistical error. Similarly, no significant change was noted in 3Point-bending; the decrease in the stiffness was approximately 4% whereas practically no change was observed in the flexural strength. On the contrary that was not the case for short-beam shear. In particular, the removal of the sizing led to an approximately 25% drop in the

short-beam shear strength. The effect of the fibre sizing burn-off on the performance can clearly be seen in Figure 4, where a large difference in the applied load of approximately 30% between the two systems is evident.

Figure 4: Comparison of representative stress-strain curves in compression.

Figure 5: Comparison of representative stress-strain curves in flexure.

Figure 6: Comparison of representative load-deflection curves in short-beam shear.

4 DISCUSSION

The results from the mechanical testing of the T650/MHT-R presented in this study suggested that this system exhibited good overall stiffness and strength properties in tension, compression, flexure and short-beam shear. However, to provide a practical meaning and place these experimental results in a wider perspective, a comparison with other carbon polyimide or carbon/epoxy multidirectional composites is essential. Considering available data in the literature and these preliminary tests at ambient temperature, the T650/MHT-R composites exhibit indeed very good stiffness properties. Nevertheless, both in tension and compression strength properties of the T650/MHT-R composites appear slightly inferior to other similar materials but comparable with carbon/epoxy multidirectional composites. In short-beam shear and flexure, even though compared to four-point bending results, T650/MHT-R composites exhibit comparable short-beam shear strength as well as flexural stiffness and strength in comparison to reported results in the literature.

In addition, in light of studies on other commercial polyimides where the sizing had been removed prior to manufacturing without sufficient reasoning, a test campaign was carried out to assess the effect of sizing on this polyimide based system. The results from the mechanical testing indicated a rather low difference in both stiffness and strength (within experimental scatter), apart from short-beam shear where a decrease of approximately 25% in the strength was noted.

To investigate this large decrease in the interlaminar strength (Figure 6) which is not in accordance with the rather small changes observed in tension (Figure 3), compression (Figure 4) and 3-Point bending (Figure 5), optical microscopy was conducted on ILSS specimens from both systems. Representative cross-sections of failed T650/MHT-R and DS-T650/MHT-R specimens are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8 and Figure 9 respectively [18]. Considering the cross section of the failed specimen shown in Figure 7, ply splitting especially in the off-axis plies pointing towards the loading point as well as delamination at the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ ply interface were the main failure mechanisms occurred in the T650/MHT-R specimen. Given the loading configuration, the amount of ply splits and the limited delamination extent, intralaminar fracture seems to have occurred first inducing subsequently in the failure process the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ delamination (red dashed line), which did not propagate towards the free edge due to the loading halt.

Figure 7: Representative micrograph of the cross section of a T650/MHT-R ILSS specimen ($\times 2.5$).

On the contrary, in the DS-T650/MHT-R specimens shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, the fracture morphology was more distributed and complex. In particular, apart from the dominant delamination at the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ ply interface in the vicinity of the midplane, multiple delaminations were noted through the specimen thickness at $-45^\circ/0^\circ$, $90^\circ/45^\circ$ and $0^\circ/0^\circ$ ply interfaces as well as excessive intralaminar damage in the 90° and off-axis plies. Judging from the fracture morphology in both DS-T650/MHT-R specimens, delaminations and transverse cracking seem to have influenced the failure process and thus the mechanical performance to a greater extent than in the T650/MHT-R specimens. In particular, delaminations, which initiated by intralaminar cracking formed in the vicinity of the loading point and propagated all the way to the free edge via migration through multiple ply splits, were evident.

Figure 8: Representative micrograph of the cross section of a DS-T650/MHT-R ILSS specimen ($\times 2.5$).

Figure 9: Representative micrograph of the cross section of a DS-T650/MHT-R ILSS specimen ($\times 2.5$).

In light of the evidence from optical microscopy, the lower intralaminar shear strength (Table 1 and Figure 6) of the DS-T650/MHT-R specimens can be attributed to the inherently lower fibre/matrix interfacial strength which caused excessive transverse cracking early in the loading scheme. Such excessive cracking induced multiple delaminations in various ply interfaces rather than a single ply interfaces as seen in the T650/MHT-R specimen (Figure 9). The low interfacial strength, (potential cause of ply cracking) can be directly related to the removal of the sizing since this process is conducted among others to enhance the adhesion between the fibres and the matrix. Taking into consideration these results, the removal of sizing is clearly not beneficial and thus is not recommended especially in applications where matrix and fibre/matrix dominated properties are important. Nevertheless, to provide a more thorough explanation on the effect of the sizing on the microstructure in this type of polyimide-based systems, further investigation is required.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The current study documents the mechanical testing of carbon fibre-reinforced polyimide composites carried out within the framework of the HicTac project. In particular, multidirectional composite specimens made of Thornel[®] T650 8-harness satin weave carbon fabric (CYTEC) and the recently developed polyimide thermosetting resin NEXIMID[®] MHT-R, were tested in tension, compression, flexure and short-beam shear. In brief, the results from the experimental procedure were: tensile stiffness and strength – 48 GPa and 471 MPa, compressive stiffness and strength – 47 GPa and 365 MPa, flexural modulus and strength 30 GPa and 485 MPa and interlaminar shear strength 48 MPa.

From the study reported in this paper the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The carbon-fibre reinforced composite materials based on the newly developed NEXIMID[®] MHT-R resin (with T_g in the excess of 400°C) exhibited comparable behavior with other commercial polyimides with much lower reported T_g .
- The removal of the sizing from the carbon fabric prior to manufacturing had a minor effect on the mechanical properties in tension, compression and flexure while in short-beam shear the effect was more pronounced; the ILSS was deteriorated by 25%.
- From this study, the removal of the fibre sizing as has been reported in the literature for other commercial polyimides is not justified.

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